

Rare earth-diamond hybrid structures for optical quantum technologies

Ionuț Gabriel Balașa*† María Alejandra Arranz-Martinez*† Pauline Perrin Midrel Ngandeu Ngambou
Alexandre Hebbrecht Diana Serrano Jocelyn Achard Alexandre Tallaire Philippe Goldner*

Dr. Ionuț Gabriel Balașa, (ionut-gabriel.balasa@chimieparistech.psl.eu), María Alejandra Arranz-Martinez, (ma.arranz-martinez@chimieparistech.psl.eu), Pauline Perrin, Alexandre Hebbrecht, Dr. Diana Serrano, Dr. Alexandre Tallaire, Dr. Philippe Goldner, (philippe.goldner@chimieparistech.psl.eu), Address: Chimie ParisTech, PSL University, CNRS, Institut de Recherche de Chimie Paris, 75005 Paris, France

Dr. Midrel Ngandeu Ngambou, Prof. Jocelyn Achard,

Address: LSPM, CNRS, Université Sorbonne Paris Nord, 99 Avenue JB Clément 93460, Villetaneuse, France

†: these authors equally contributed to the work.

Keywords: *quantum technology, rare earth, diamond, color centers, optical spectroscopy, thin films, CVD*

Diamond containing nitrogen-vacancy centers (NV^-) is one of the most investigated materials for quantum technologies, because of this system's exceptional spin properties. Although the NV^- optical transition is very bright, it suffers from spectral diffusion and weak zero-phonon line, and is in the visible range. This limits integration into quantum photonic structures and interfacing with optical fiber networks. In contrast, rare earth (RE) ions exhibit extremely narrow and stable optical transitions, including erbium's 1.5 μm telecom wavelength. Combining RE with NV^- properties through short-range interactions is however challenging as RE do not readily enter the diamond lattice.

In this work, a thin-film-based architecture in which RE and NV^- centers can interact while preserving their unique properties is introduced. Thin films of $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ are grown by chemical vapor deposition on diamond substrates with well-crystallized and highly textured structures. An extensive spectroscopic study of Er^{3+} transitions at room and low temperatures further reveals that photoluminescence spectra and decays are close to bulk materials. We also show that Y_2O_3 thin film deposition has no detrimental effects on NV^- optical and spin properties. RE thin films deposited on diamond could thus be suitable for building hybrid materials for new functionalities in quantum sensing, communication, and processing.

1 Introduction

Color centers in diamond are actively investigated for applications in quantum technologies that combine optical and spin degrees of freedom [1]. Among them, the negatively charged nitrogen vacancy center (NV^-) stands out as an optically addressable spin system with exceptional properties [2]. Indeed, it is a very bright emitter that enables efficient optical detection of electron spin states by fluorescence intensity monitoring. These spin states have moreover very long coherence lifetimes, up to milliseconds at room temperature [3]. These unique features have triggered numerous studies and led to striking demonstrations in quantum sensing [4], communications [5], and computing [6], the most prominent application being the detection of weak constant or varying magnetic fields [7], at the nanoscale [8], or under extreme conditions [9].

It could be still very useful to enhance some of the NV^- properties, particularly its optical transition, which tends to suffer from significant frequency instability, known as the spectral diffusion effect, and has a weak zero phonon line [2]. Moreover, it is located in the visible range, which makes photonic integration and interfacing with optical telecom fibers difficult. This is a central motivation for the strong interest in

developing other color centers in diamond [10] and related materials, such as SiC [11]. Another approach would be to make NV^- centers interact with another system to provide the required properties. Of particular interest are the rare earth (RE) ions which are well-known quantum emitters with ultra-narrow optical homogeneous linewidths [12]. At low temperatures, these linewidths can be as small as a few kHz and down to 75 Hz, exhibit low spectral diffusion, and can be found in the infrared range [13]. In this respect, Er^{3+} ions are especially useful because they have a transition at 1.5 μm , in the telecom C-band [14]. RE favorable properties motivate the development of quantum memories for light [15], microwave to optical transducers [16], or sources of indistinguishable photons [16]. However, these outstanding properties in the solid state, can only be obtained in well-chosen hosts, typically high-quality oxide crystals such as Y_2SiO_5 , $CaWO_4$, or Y_2O_3 [13]. In particular, RE ions are difficult to introduce into diamond and the attempts reported so far did not show the well-resolved optical lines found in the above-mentioned crystals [17, 18]. Composite materials based on RE-doped nanoparticles embedded in polycrystalline diamond have also been produced for application as luminescent X-Ray detectors [19, 20]. However, they lack the high-quality environment of NV^- centers in single crystalline diamond.

Here we propose an approach in which a RE doped oxide thin film is deposited on top of a single crystalline diamond substrate that contains NV^- centers. First, this enables RE ions to sit in a chemically suitable environment through substitution of host cations with similar valence and atomic radii, and high coordination number. Second, Eu^{3+} and Er^{3+} doped Y_2O_3 thin films deposited on Si have shown homogeneous linewidths in the range of a MHz to a few kHz, making them promising platforms for integrated optical quantum technologies [21, 22]. In a $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ /diamond hybrid structure, Er^{3+} ions can interact with shallow NV^- centers and provide them with a high-quality optical quantum transition at the telecom wavelength. Interactions between the two centers can take place through magnetic dipole-dipole coupling as Er^{3+} is a paramagnetic ion with an effective 1/2 spin for which, moreover, g values as large as 12 can be observed [23]. Finally, the thin film architecture is also ideal for integration into optoelectronic systems for the development of scalable quantum nanophotonic devices [24, 25].

In this work, we grew $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ thin films on single crystalline diamond substrates by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and studied their structural and optical properties. Our results demonstrate that well-crystallized and strongly textured polycrystalline films can be obtained at deposition temperatures between 650 and 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. A detailed room and low temperature spectroscopic study of the two main transitions of Er^{3+} ions in the visible and near IR reveals that these films have a high-crystalline quality and low concentration of defects. Hence, at low Er^{3+} concentrations, photoluminescence (PL) decay lifetimes at 1.5 μm can reach up to 16 ms, identical to values measured in bulk single crystals [13]. We also studied the effect of oxide thin film deposition on the PL and spin transitions of shallow NV^- centers and observed that their spectral properties are fully preserved after deposition of a Y_2O_3 film, despite harsh conditions of high temperature and oxygen atmosphere. These findings pave the way towards new hybrid materials for optical quantum technologies such as quantum nodes for communication and processing, and distributed quantum sensing.

Figure 1: Hybrid materials structural properties. (a) Rare earth/diamond structures studied in this work (thicknesses not to scale). (b) XRD patterns of the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films on (100) diamond substrates for different deposition temperatures ($550 \leq T_{\text{dep}} \leq 1000$ °C) and reference pattern for a randomly oriented Y_2O_3 powder (PDF Card - 00-041-1105). The observed diffraction peaks of Y_2O_3 are identified on top of the graphs. Other peaks and broad features are due to the sample holder and fixing material. Films obtained for $T_{\text{dep}} \leq 750$ °C and $T_{\text{dep}} \geq 950$ °C show strong (100) and (111) textures, respectively. (c-e) SEM images of samples deposited at 750 °C, 850 °C and 950 °C with typical grain shapes highlighted. (f) Thin film grain sizes estimated from XRD using the Scherrer equation and SEM images. For 950 and 1000 °C, XRD peak widths are limited by instrumental resolution, giving a lower bound of 200 nm for grain sizes.

2 Structure and optical spectroscopy of $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin film on diamond substrates

Deposition of the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films was performed by direct liquid injection CVD (DLI-CVD) using a custom setup which has been previously described in detail [21]. Briefly, liquid precursors of Y and Er are first sprayed and evaporated at 210 °C. The vapors are then carried by nitrogen gas to the deposition chamber which is maintained at a pressure of about 15 mbar. Mixing with oxygen gas can then lead to the growth of oxide thin films on substrates heated at high temperatures, most notably silicon wafers [21, 26]. The whole process is accurately monitored and controlled using mass flow and temperature sensors.

$\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films with a 0.67% nominal doping concentration were grown on high-pressure high-temperature (HPHT) single crystalline diamond substrates with (100) orientation at deposition temperatures ranging from $T_{\text{dep}} = 550^\circ \text{C}$ up to 1000°C (**Figure 1a**, top). The thin films had a homogeneous thickness across the $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ area of the diamond substrates, with values, as measured by ellipsometry, of about 560 nm in the 650-950°C temperature range and of 120 and 790 nm at 550 and 1000 °C respectively (see SI1). Although the diamond substrates were exposed to high temperatures in an oxygen-rich atmosphere, which could induce surface oxidation [27], no changes on any sides of the substrates were noticed under visual inspection. Films were also deposited on HPHT diamond substrates overgrown by a CVD film containing implanted NV^- centers (**Figure 1a**, bottom). Additional details on the thin film deposition can be found in the Experimental Section.

2.1 Structural characterization

Figure 1b presents the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of thin films deposited at different temperatures against the powder pattern of the bixbyite cubic phase of Y_2O_3 (Ia-3, space group #206) used as a reference. Three main peaks can be identified in the thin film patterns corresponding to the (222) ($2\theta_{(222)} \sim 29.162^\circ$), (400) ($2\theta_{(400)} \sim 33.8^\circ$) and (440) ($2\theta_{(440)} \sim 48.55^\circ$) planes of the Y_2O_3 cubic structure. Because of the small surface size of the samples and thus very weak signals, a number of other spurious peaks were visible on the XRD patterns and are attributed to the sample holder and fixing material.

All XRD patterns showed strong deviations from the Y_2O_3 randomly oriented powder reference pattern, with a clear influence of T_{dep} on the relative intensities of the XRD peaks. Indeed, for $T_{\text{dep}} \leq 750^\circ \text{C}$ the (400) peak is much more intense than the (222) one, in contrast with the 1:4 ratio of the powder reference. This indicates that the thin films have a strong (100) out-of-plane texture, with a Lotgering degree of orientation $f \geq 85\%$ [28, 29]. Details of the texture calculations and values for each film are provided in SI1. A different case was observed for the thin films deposited at $T_{\text{dep}} \gtrsim 950^\circ$. Here, the (222) peak is the strongest which corresponds to a film mainly textured along the [111] direction but to a smaller degree than the low temperature films as the (440) peak has also a large intensity. Accordingly, f is in the 58-68% range. Finally, for $T_{\text{dep}} = 850^\circ$, it is the (440) peak that is the strongest, twice as intense as the (222) one, while a nearly inverse $I_{(440)}/I_{(222)} = 4/10$ intensity ratio is found on the powder. The film is therefore (110) textured with $f = 52\%$.

Film morphology was then investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). **Figure 1c**, **d**, and **e** presents SEM images of thin films deposited at three different deposition temperatures corresponding to the three texture regimes identified by XRD. These images show polycrystalline structures with faceted

grains highlighting how out-of-plane texture translates into film morphology. Indeed, for the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ film deposited at 750°C (Figure 1c) grains with a squared shape were observed, in agreement with the [100] four-fold symmetry axis determined by XRD. For $T_{\text{dep}} = 950^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 1e) the film showed grains with a triangular shape, corresponding to the [111] direction identified by XRD as it is a three-fold symmetry axis in Y_2O_3 cubic structure. Finally, at $T_{\text{dep}} \approx 850^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 1d), a mixture of square and triangular shapes is found, again in accordance with the XRD analysis.

The [100] out-of-plane growth direction for thin films deposited at $T_{\text{dep}} < 850^\circ$ could be induced by strain minimization with respect to the diamond substrate, which is also [100] oriented. Indeed, for a cube-on-cube geometry, the mismatch between Y_2O_3 and diamond lattices is only 0.9% for a 3:1 cell ratio. This also suggests that heteroepitaxy of Y_2O_3 on diamond is achievable for deposition temperatures below 850°C . For deposition temperatures above 950°C , higher thermal energy seems to favor the [111] out-of-plane growth, which corresponds to the densest atomic plane and lowest surface energy [30]. Thin films with (111) orientation have thus been observed on different substrates such as (100) Si [21, 31]. Textured films along high symmetry directions such as [100] and [111] are beneficial as they enable sub-ensembles of Er^{3+} ions to behave in the same way for light polarization or external magnetic field applied along the same directions. Thus, coherent driving of optical transitions or well-defined magnetic interactions are facilitated in these systems compared to randomly oriented ones [32].

XRD patterns and SEM images were also analyzed in terms of grain sizes (Figure 1f). Using the Scherrer formula (see SI1), we found grain sizes of 90 and 130 nm for the films grown at 650 and 750°C respectively from the (400) XRD peak, i.e. in the out-of-plane growth direction. The SEM images revealed an in-plane grain size of about 90 nm. The film obtained at 550°C presented a significantly broadened (400) peak corresponding to a smaller grain size of ≈ 45 nm together with a reduced thickness of 120 nm. This suggests that this temperature is close to the lowest at which a well-crystallized Y_2O_3 film can be obtained. At deposition temperatures of 850°C and above, the grain size perpendicular to the surface, determined from the (222) peak, increased from 120 nm to values above 200 nm (limited by the instrument), while film thicknesses remained around 560 nm and reached 790 nm for the 1000°C sample (see SI1). The in-plane grain size remained at about 100 nm (150 nm for the 1000°C film). The closeness of in- and out-of-plane grain sizes above $T_{650}^\circ\text{C}$ suggests that surface and bulk diffusion is active during the film growth [33].

Large grains are important for minimizing perturbations related to the surface, such as electric field noise created by charges or dangling bonds, on RE ions' quantum states [25]. The observed grain sizes, of at least 100 nm, should be large enough to allow for homogeneous linewidths down to 50 kHz at low RE doping, according to results obtained on nanoparticles [34, 35]. Such values are in turn sufficient to observe preliminary quantum functionalities like coherent light storage by electro-optic protocols [32]. Large grains are also favorable to long PL decays, as will be shown in the next section because they minimize PL quenching by surface defects.

2.1.1 $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ optical spectroscopy

We next studied the spectroscopic properties of Er^{3+} ions in Y_2O_3 thin films deposited at temperatures between 650 and 1000°C . The film deposited at 550°C gave a very low signal, presumably because of its insufficient crystalline quality, and will not be discussed in the following.

Figure 2: Optical properties of the green emission of Er^{3+} in Y_2O_3 thin films grown on diamond substrates at deposition temperatures T_{dep} between 650 and 1000 °C. (a) Room temperature (RT) photo-luminescence (PL) corresponding to the $(^2\text{H}_{11/2}, ^4\text{S}_{3/2}) \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transitions between crystal field levels (see main text and SI2). Spectra are normalized to the strongest peak at 565 nm assigned to the $\text{E}_1 \rightarrow \text{Z}_{7,8}$ transitions between crystal field levels (see main text and SI2). (b) PL spectra of the $^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transition at 10 K. The $\text{E}_1 \rightarrow \text{Z}_1$ and $\text{E}_1 \rightarrow \text{Z}_{7,8}$ transitions are highlighted at 548.3 and 565 nm, respectively. Spectra are normalized to the strongest peak at 565 nm. (c) Er^{3+} concentration, determined by RBS and PL intensity, as a function of thin film deposition temperature T_{dep} . (d) Room temperature energy transfer parameter of the Inokuti-Hirayama model (see main text) as a function of Er^{3+} concentration. Line: fit to a linear function. (e,f) RT and 10 K $^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ PL decays measured at 565 nm following pulsed excitation at 520 nm. Lines: fitted curves using the Inokuti-Hirayama model (see main text). Decays and fits for all samples are presented in SI3. (g,h) $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ level lifetime, extracted from the exponential tail of the RT and 10 K PL decays in (e,f), as a function of deposition temperature.

The unit cell of cubic Y_2O_3 includes two different sites for Y^{3+} that Er^{3+} ions can substitute: a C_2 site (24-fold multiplicity) with a two-fold symmetry axis along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions and a C_{3i} site (8-fold multiplicity) with a three-fold symmetry axis along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions and an inversion center. Given the close atomic radii between Y^{3+} and Er^{3+} (0.892 Å and 0.881 Å [36]), it is likely that the site occupancy also follows a 1 to 3 ratio. Electric dipole (ED) transitions are forbidden for Er^{3+} ions in C_{3i} sites due to the inversion center [37]. In this case, only magnetic dipole (MD) transitions obeying the selection rule $\Delta J = 0, \pm 1$ have non-vanishing intensity. Because of this, ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ was the only transition we observed for the C_{3i} ions.

Before reporting on Er^{3+} telecom wavelength transition at 1.5 μm , we present the results obtained on emission in the green spectral range that gives important insights on Er^{3+} concentration and ion-ion interactions.

Green emission

Figure 2a presents the room temperature PL spectra of Er^{3+} in the 530-570 nm range for different films. They were obtained after exciting the ${}^4\text{I}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ transition at 520 nm with a pulsed optical parametric oscillator (see Experimental Section and SI2 for energy level schemes). The emission lines correspond to ED transitions (ions in C_2 sites) from the ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ and ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ multiplets to the ${}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ ground one. The spectra of the films deposited at all temperatures between 650 and 1000 °C were nearly identical in terms of peak position, widths, and relative intensities and matched those of Y_2O_3 bulk references [38]. This is the first indication that Er^{3+} ions sit in a high-quality crystalline environment in the thin films.

For the PL spectra recorded at 10 K (Figure 2b), only 7 different emission lines were identified, corresponding to transitions from the lowest ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ crystal field (CF) level (E_1) to the 8 CF levels ($Z_1 - Z_8$) of ${}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ [39, 40] (see SI2). The narrowest peak in the PL spectrum corresponds to the $E_1 \rightarrow Z_1$ transition at 548.3 nm in Figure 2b. Its full width at half maximum (FWHM) across the different samples was slightly below 10 cm^{-1} or 0.3 nm, essentially instrument-limited.

We also recorded PL spectra at room temperature on a microscopy setup for which acquisition conditions (especially light collection and laser intensity) could be accurately controlled (see Experimental Section). Although PL maps showed consistent intensities across each film's surface, large variations were found between e.g. the 650 and 1000 °C films. They could not be explained by changes in PL decays, film thicknesses, or shifts in absorption lines, and are therefore attributed to varying Er^{3+} concentrations. Since all the experimental parameters but the deposition temperature were kept constant for the different depositions, e.g., molar flow and evaporation temperature of precursors, or deposition chamber pressure, changes in erbium concentration are ascribed to differences in reactivity or stability between the $\text{Y}(\text{TMHD})_3$ and $\text{Er}(\text{TMHD})_3$ precursors as a function of temperature. Er^{3+} concentrations were estimated from PL intensities, corrected for film thickness and decay times (1/e values), and a Rutherford backscattering (RBS) measurement on the film deposited at 650 °C. They decreased with increasing T_{dep} in a nearly linear tendency, from 1 to 0.05 % for a constant nominal concentration of 0.67% (Figure 2c).

Room-temperature decays for samples deposited at 650, 850, and 1000 °C are shown in Figure 2e and others in SI3. Initially, they exhibit a fast non-exponential drop that gradually evolves into an exponential tail. They become longer and closer to a single-exponential as deposition temperature is increased, i.e. Er^{3+} concentration decreases. This behavior is typical of:

1. the relaxation of excited ions (the so-called donors, D) towards quenching centers (the acceptors, A) by an energy transfer process. It varies from donor to donor because of changes in the location of acceptors around each donor [41, 42]. This D→A process leads to an $\exp(-t^{3/s})$ initial time dependence in the donor decay for a s -multipolar interaction mechanism, assuming a random and continuous D-A distance distribution [43].
2. migration of excitation by energy transfer between donors before transfer to an acceptor [41, 42], i.e. a D→D→...→D→A mechanism. In this way, donors which were not initially excited can also relax with a nearby acceptor. These delayed relaxations result in an exponential tail for the donor decay because the migration steps smooth out the D-A distance distribution.
3. in addition, donors can also relax without energy transfers by radiative and non-radiative processes. At very low donor and acceptor concentrations, these are the only operating mechanisms and decays are single-exponential.

We could well fit experimental PL decays $I(t)$ with the expression established by Inokuti and Hirayama for dipole-dipole interaction between donors and acceptors ($s = 6$) [43]:

$$I(t) = I_0 \exp\left(-\frac{4}{3}\pi^{3/2}N_A\sqrt{C \cdot t}\right) \exp(-t/\tau). \quad (1)$$

Here, the first and second exponential terms refer to processes 1 and 2,3 respectively. N_A is the acceptor concentration, and C accounts for the energy transfer strength. To take into account energy migration, the exponential tail decay rate is expressed as $1/\tau = 1/\tau_0 + 1/\tau_D$, where the first term corresponds to the isolated donor (process 3) and the second one to the relaxation caused by energy migration (process 2) [41]. A more complex equation has been proposed to describe the D→A and D→D processes [44] but it did not lead to better fits and was not used in our analysis.

To identify the quenching centers, we first plotted $N_A\sqrt{C}$ as a function of the Er^{3+} concentration N_{Er} (Figure 2d). A strong linear correlation is found, clearly pointing to Er^{3+} as both the donor and the acceptor species. Indeed, ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ relaxation can proceed through the cross-relaxations (${}^4\text{S}_{3/2} - {}^2\text{H}_{11/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$) → (${}^4\text{I}_{13/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{9/2}$) (see SI3), which are resonant within one-phonon energy [40]. This dipole-dipole energy transfer is predicted to occur only for ions in C_2 symmetry because of selection rules (see SI3), and we deduce $C = 1.8 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-42} \text{ cm}^6\text{s}^{-1}$. The exponential tail of the decays is then attributed to energy migration within the C_2 ions, corresponding to the (${}^4\text{S}_{3/2} - {}^2\text{H}_{11/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$) → (${}^4\text{I}_{15/2}, {}^4\text{S}_{3/2} - {}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$) energy transfer, followed by the same cross-relaxation as above (see SI3). The corresponding lifetimes are shown in Figure 2g. In this model $1/\tau_D \propto N_A N_D$ [41] and thus in our case $1/\tau_D \propto N_{Er}^2$. Although τ variations with N_{Er} are relatively small compared to error bars, data are compatible with this dependence (see SI3).

At low temperatures, the decays were longer, with the same behavior, but with a reduced evolution with T_{dep} (Figure 2f,h, and SI3). Modeling the decays with **Equation 1** led to $C = 5 \pm 1 \times 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^6\text{s}^{-1}$, a lower value than at room temperature (see SI3). This can be due to a decrease in transition linewidths, phonon occupancy, or changes in populations of the levels involved in the energy transfer.

These analyses show that the decay variations in the films are mainly due to changes in Er^{3+} concentration, whereas the effect of other possible quenching centers is not observed, likely due to low defect concentrations. Especially, at the highest deposition temperature, we observed single exponential decays

explained by a low N_{Er} which prevents both energy migration and cross-relaxations within the Er^{3+} ions.

These conclusions are supported by the comparison with bulk materials. Indeed, the values found in the thin film deposited at 1000 °C ($N_{Er} = 0.05\%$), are close to those found in high-quality ceramics obtained at high temperatures and doped at 0.2 % [45]: $\tau(\text{thin film, 300 K}) = 112 \mu\text{s}$, $\tau(\text{ceramic, 300 K}) = 88 \mu\text{s}$, $\tau(\text{thin film, 10 K}) = 168 \mu\text{s}$, $\tau(\text{ceramic, 10 K}) = 155 \mu\text{s}$.

Infrared transition at 1.5 μm

As mentioned in the introduction, Er^{3+} telecom wavelength emission at 1.5 μm is of great interest for quantum communication and integrated photonics. PL spectra of the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transition were first recorded at room temperature after excitation of the ${}^2H_{11/2}$ level of Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 sites at 520 nm (see SI2 for energy level schemes). As for the green emission, the samples grown at different deposition temperatures all showed spectra close to those reported in bulk materials [46]. They exhibit a strong peak at 1535.5 nm corresponding to the $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_1$ and $Y_2 \rightarrow Z_2$ CF transitions of Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 sites (**Figure 3a** and SI2) [47, 23]. Relative peak intensities are very close across the samples, except for the line at 1548 nm which is mainly due to the MD $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_2$ transition of ions in C_{3i} sites (see SI2). Its intensity decreased compared to the 1535.5 nm peak as T_{dep} increased. This is explained by an energy transfer from ions in the C_2 sites towards those in the C_{3i} sites. It decreases with decreasing N_{Er} , and thus with increasing T_{dep} .

At 10 K, as presented in Figure 3b, 7 lines were observed and attributed to Er^{3+} ions in both C_2 and C_{3i} sites relaxing mainly from the lowest Y_1 CF level to the Z_n ground state levels (see SI2). With fewer and narrower lines, the variations in relative intensity between the C_2 1535.5 and C_{3i} 1548 nm lines are even more pronounced than at room temperature (Figure 3b). The zoom in the 1530-1560 nm range shown in Figure 3c highlights the decrease of the C_{3i} line intensity with increasing T_{dep} , i.e. decreasing Er^{3+} concentration. It eventually vanishes for the sample deposited at 1000°C.

To get further insight into these energy transfer effects, the decay dynamics of the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transition in the two sites were investigated at 10 K. This enabled excitation and monitoring of the C_2 and C_{3i} ions separately. More precisely, PL decays for Er^{3+} in C_2 sites were recorded by exciting the $Z_1 \rightarrow Y_2$ transition at 1528 nm while collecting emission from the $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_1$ transition at 1535.5 nm (Figure 3d and f). Similarly, for Er^{3+} ions in C_{3i} sites, the $Z_1 \rightarrow Y_2$ transition was excited at 1530.5 nm and the $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_2$ emission recorded at 1548 nm (Figure 3d and g). In contrast to the green emission, all decays are single exponential except for the C_2 ions in the sample deposited at 650 °C.

Following the analysis of the green transition decays, we reach the following conclusions (see SI4 for details):

1. for Er^{3+} ions in the C_{3i} sites, energy migration towards quenching centers such as impurities or defects on the surface or in the volume of the crystalline grains are responsible for the changes in the PL decays. They are likely to be in very low concentrations, given the long lifetimes ($\tau \geq 12$ ms) observed for all samples. Moreover, their concentration is likely to be independent of deposition temperature, which we deduced from the linear dependence of $1/\tau$ against N_{Er} .
2. for Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 sites, energy migration followed by relaxation towards the C_{3i} ions explains the evolution of the decays and relative PL intensities. This energy transfer is favored by the Y_1 level of C_2 ions lying at 42 cm^{-1} above that of the C_{3i} ions (Figure 3d and SI4). In addition, in the 650 °C sample, the exponential component at long times is ascribed to back-transfer from C_{3i} ions.

The very long lifetimes (≥ 15 and 8 ms, Figure 3e) for the C_{3i} and C_2 ions in samples deposited at 950 and 1000 °C are similar to those of a bulk crystal at the same concentration [48]. We therefore reach the same conclusion than for the green transition, i.e. that our materials present a low concentration of quenching defects or impurities. Moreover, it seems to be independent of deposition temperature which makes useful a broad range of deposition conditions, for e.g. selecting film out-of-plane growth directions and possibly obtaining epitaxy.

2.2 Shallow NV^- centers properties in a hybrid structure

The conditions we used for the deposition of Y_2O_3 thin films expose diamond substrates to high temperatures (up to 1000°C) in an oxygen-rich atmosphere, which could induce oxidation of the diamond surface. This is to be avoided as optical and spin properties of shallow NV^- centers could be affected, preventing useful interactions with rare earth ions at the oxide-diamond interface.

As mentioned above, HPHT diamond substrates used in the previous section did not show visible signs of surface damage. To further check the absence of degradation of the diamond, a 200 nm Y_2O_3 thin film was deposited at 850 °C on a high-purity CVD-grown diamond film where shallow NV^- centers have been previously created by implantation (Figure 1a) [49]. More specifically, two 1 mm diameter spots were implanted with N_2^+ ions at 5 and 10 keV energies and a fluence of 1.8×10^{13} ions/cm², resulting in ppm levels of NV^- centers 4.5 nm and 8 nm deep, according to simulations (see Experimental Section).

First, the NV^- center PL signal of the zero phonon line (ZPL) at 637 nm was mapped across the 3x3 mm² diamond substrate under excitation at 532 nm (**Figure 4a,b**). Before the Y_2O_3 film deposition, the two circular implanted areas can be easily identified against the non-implanted background. The PL intensity of the 8 nm depth spot is brighter than for the 4.5 nm depth one, due to a higher NV^- creation yield at higher energies [50]. After carefully ensuring stable experimental conditions and normalizing PL to the diamond Raman peak at 573 nm, we recorded NV^- PL intensities after the Y_2O_3 film deposition and found values, averaged over each spot, within 10% of the initial ones. This confirms that NV^- centers were not etched during the deposition step and preserved their optical properties. Similar results were obtained for amorphous Al_2O_3 films deposited on diamond but at significantly lower temperature (200 °C) [51].

Figures 4c and 4d show typical PL spectra close to the center of the 4.5 and 8 nm depth implanted spots, before and after the deposition. The emissions are mainly due to the NV^- center, which ZPL appears at 637 nm, with a small contribution from the NV^0 center denoted by a ZPL at 575 nm [52]. After deposition, the intensity of the band at $\lambda \geq 720$ nm decreased compared to the NV^- ZPL and NV^- vibronic lines ($637 \leq \lambda < 750$ nm), suggesting lesser structural defects. This is attributed to the annealing of the diamond substrate at 850° C during the Y_2O_3 thin film deposition.

The spin properties of the implanted NV^- centers ($S = 1$) were also probed before and after deposition by optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR) using confocal microscopy (see Experimental Section). Here, a microwave field is scanned in frequency over the NV^- centers spin transitions ($m_S = 0 \rightarrow m_S = \pm 1$) while their PL is monitored. The optical excitation induces spin polarisation in the $m_S = 0$ level and results in a strong PL, which decreases when transitions to the $m_S = \pm 1$ levels occur. This is due to the spin-dependent relaxations of the NV^- excited state [2]. To better observe the spin transitions linewidths, a static magnetic field \vec{B} was applied to the sample to split the $m_S = \pm 1$ transitions. Moreover, \vec{B} was set

Figure 3: Optical properties of the $1.5 \mu\text{m } ^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition of Er^{3+} in Y_2O_3 thin films grown on diamond substrates at deposition temperatures T_{dep} between 650 and 1000 °C. Room temperature (a) and 10 K (b) $^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ PL spectra. The $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_1$ transition of Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 sites at 1535.5 nm, as well as the $Y_1 \rightarrow Z_2$ transition of ions in the C_{3i} sites at 1548 nm are denoted by dashed lines. Spectra are normalized to the strongest peak. (c) Zoom of (b) in the 1530 - 1565 nm range with PL spectra normalized to the C_2 peak at 1535.5 nm (blue dashed line). The C_{3i} ions peak at 1548 nm (orange dashed line) strongly varies with T_{dep} , highlighting site to site energy transfer (see main text). (d) Partial energy level scheme of Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 and C_{3i} sites. Excitation and emission transitions are indicated by solid lines and non-radiative relaxations by dotted ones. (e) $^4I_{13/2}$ level lifetimes of Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 and C_{3i} sites as a function of T_{dep} . In the case of the double exponential fit (C_2 ions and $T_{dep} = 650$ °C) the shortest value is plotted. (f,g) Empty circles: PL decays of Er^{3+} ions in C_{3i} and C_2 sites at 10 K obtained by exciting the transitions at 1530.5 nm ($C_{3i}:Z_1 \rightarrow Y_2$) and 1528 nm ($C_2:Z_1 \rightarrow Y_2$) respectively. Solid lines: fits using single exponentials except for the C_2 ions in the film deposited at 650 °C which follows a double exponential function (see main text). All decays and fits are presented in S14.

Figure 4: Spin and optical properties of shallow NV^- centers before and after deposition of a 200 nm Y_2O_3 film at 850 °C. (a,b) NV^- PL of the entire 3×3 mm² sample measured with green excitation at 532 nm and monitored at 637 nm. The two spots with strong emission correspond to nitrogen implantation at 4.5 and 8 nm depth. (c,d) Typical spectra acquired in the two implantation spots. All spectra are normalized to maximum intensity. (e) ODMR spectra at the center of the 8 nm depth spot. PL contrast was obtained by normalizing the signal at 2730 MHz. The four pairs of peaks symmetrically distributed around the 2870 MHz center frequency correspond to the different orientations of the NV^- centers in the diamond lattice (see main text). (f) High-resolution spectra of the 2770 MHz lines in (e). Fits with three Lorentzian functions (solid lines) give linewidths of 3.2 ± 0.2 and 3.4 ± 0.2 MHz before and after Y_2O_3 film deposition.

to a direction such that the transitions corresponding to the four possible orientations of the NV^- centers, along the $\langle 111 \rangle$ directions of the diamond cubic lattice, were also distinct.

Figure 4e shows ODMR spectra of the implanted NV^- centers at 8 nm depth before and after the deposition of the Y_2O_3 thin film at two close locations. Eight lines can be identified due to the $m_S = 0 \rightarrow m_S = -1$ transitions (below 2870 MHz) and $m_S = 0 \rightarrow m_S = +1$ ones (over 2870 MHz). On this scale, it can already be seen that the PL contrast and spin transition linewidths are very similar. The slightly different line positions and strengths are ascribed to a small change in \vec{B} orientation between experiments. High-resolution scans of the line at 2770 MHz confirmed these results (Figure 4f). In these spectra, three components can be observed, due to interactions between the NV^- electron spin and the ^{14}N ($I = 1$) nuclear spin [2]. A fit with three Lorentzian functions gave linewidths of 3.2 ± 0.2 MHz before Y_2O_3 deposition and 3.4 ± 0.2 MHz afterward. Spectra taken at other locations similarly show identical linewidths within 300 kHz before and after the Y_2O_3 film deposition. These values are ascribed to inhomogeneous broadening induced by the high concentration of implanted nitrogen and damages to the crystal lattice due to the implantation [7]. The lack of increase in linewidth and decrease of PL contrast indicates that NV^- spin properties such as population lifetimes and inhomogeneous broadening are preserved after the Y_2O_3 thin film deposition.

3 Conclusion

Thin films of Y_2O_3 were grown by DLI-CVD on (100) diamond single crystals heated at temperatures between 550 and 1000 °C. The films were well-crystallized above 650 °C and showed strong (100) and (111) textures depending on deposition temperature T_{dep} , as shown by XRD and SEM. In these samples, crystalline grains' smallest dimension was at least 100 nm, with larger values observed at higher deposition temperatures.

PL of Er^{3+} doped films was investigated at room and low temperatures in the green and infrared regions corresponding to the $^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ and $^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ transitions. Emission spectra were found to be close to those reported for bulk materials, indicating a high crystalline quality of the samples. Their intensity however varied with deposition temperature due to a change in Er^{3+} concentration from 1 to 0.05 % when T_{dep} increased from 650 to 1000 °C. This was attributed to different reactivities and stabilities between the $\text{Er}(\text{TMHD})_3$ and $\text{Y}(\text{TMHD})_3$ precursors.

A detailed study of the PL decays revealed that they were driven by energy migration and energy transfer between Er^{3+} ions. At high T_{dep} , where these phenomena are much reduced because of the low Er^{3+} concentration, we recorded long lifetimes, similar to bulk crystals. Especially, lifetimes up to 15.8 ms were obtained for the $^4\text{I}_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ telecom wavelength transition at 10 K. This highlights the low concentration of defects able to quench luminescence in our thin films. Moreover, our analysis suggests that the defect concentration is independent of T_{dep} , enabling growing high-quality films under a broad range of conditions. For example, this could be useful to exploit specific out-of-plane textures.

Finally, shallow NV^- centers were created by implantation at 4.5 and 8 nm depth in a high-purity CVD diamond film. Their PL under green excitation showed no change in intensity after deposition of a 200 nm Y_2O_3 thin film at 850 °C, despite the presence of oxygen during the high-temperature film growth. Spin transitions linewidths and PL contrasts recorded by ODMR were also found unchanged, showing that NV^- spin properties were preserved after film deposition.

These results are promising for the creation of film-based hybrid structures in which Er^{3+} ions and NV^- centers can interact while preserving their exceptional properties. The high crystalline quality of the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films should in particular enable observing narrow homogeneous linewidths, i.e. long quantum state lifetimes, as shown in Y_2O_3 nanoparticles of similar grain sizes [34]. This can be probed by experiments such as spectral hole burning [21] or saturation spectroscopy [53], while pulsed ODMR can assess NV^- spin coherence lifetimes [7]. Further improvement in Er^{3+} properties could be obtained by epitaxial growth of Y_2O_3 on diamond, which could be possible given the very good lattice match between the two materials. It can moreover be noted that oxide epitaxial films on diamond have been obtained for compounds like EuO [54] or Ga_2O_3 [55] for example. Finally, films with low Er^{3+} concentrations, down to the 10s of ppm range, can be grown by DLI-CVD, which would decrease Er^{3+} - Er^{3+} interactions and the associated decoherence [22].

Moreover, our thin film architecture allows for multiple optimizations such as growing multi-layered structures with tight control on thicknesses and doping levels that could be useful e.g. for moving away active ions from film outer surfaces [21, 56]. It is also ideally suited to fully use NV^- centers in diamond CVD films, which provide the best performances for quantum technologies [4]. The RE-diamond hybrid materials reported in this work are thus an attractive approach to designing new devices that combine the unique quantum properties of the two systems for applications to networks for quantum communication,

computing, and sensing.

4 Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (RareDiamond, grant agreement No 101019234) and the 80 prime CNRS project Mathyq. We thank Dr. Carlo Scian for the RBS measurements.

5 Experimental Section

Thin film growth

Thin film growth was performed in a custom-made Direct Liquid Injection (DLI) CVD reactor described in [26], with independent injection of Y and Er precursors. For convenience, the main characteristics of the setup are given below.

High purity (5N) crystalline solids of beta-diketonate complexes ($\text{Er}(\text{TMHD})_3$ and $\text{Y}(\text{TMHD})_3$) were purchased from EPIVALENCE. Precursors were diluted in mesitylene (99% purity from Fischer Scientific) with concentrations of 0.25 mM and 10 mM, respectively. Thin film nominal composition (0.67% Er^{3+}) doping was ensured through accurate monitoring and adjustment of the liquid precursors flows in the vaporization chamber heated at 210 °C (Keamstream Vapbox 1500).

Vaporized precursors were carried by a N_2 flow (400 sccm) towards the reaction chamber where they were adsorbed on the heated substrate and reacted with the oxygen gas (150 sccm) to grow the Y_2O_3 thin film. The sample holder could be heated up to 1000°C while the pressure in the chamber was fixed at around 15 mbar. Before deposition, the (100) HPHT single crystal diamond substrates (Sumimoto, type Ib) were cleaned by sonicating in absolute ethanol.

Structural and morphological characterization

The oxide growth rate was estimated from the thin film thicknesses measured by ex-situ Spectroscopic Ellipsometry (SE) performed with a Woollam iSE system at a fixed incidence angle of 65°. Crystalline phase, texture, and grain size were determined through X-ray Diffraction (XRD) in a Panalytical XPert Pro diffractometer using a copper anode ($K_\alpha = 8.04 \text{ keV}$; 1.5406 \AA). Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) investigation of the surface morphology of the Y_2O_3 thin films was performed with a Zeiss Supra FE-SEM.

NV^- center implantation

Before implantation, a 20 μm thick high purity CVD diamond layer was grown on type Ib high-pressure high temperature (100)-oriented diamond substrate by microwave plasma assisted CVD [52]. The custom setup used afterward for the implantation of shallow NV^- centers is detailed in [57]. Since the ion beam diameter is on the order of 10 mm², a copper mask with a 1 mm diameter hole was used as a shadow mask to obtain implanted spots. N_2^+ ion beam energies of 5 keV and 10 keV with a fluence of 1.8×10^{13} ions/cm² resulted in the implantation of nitrogen at 4.5 and 8 nm according to SRIM simulations. After the implantation, thermal annealing was performed at 800 °C for 2 h in vacuum to increase NV^- centers

concentration. The latter was estimated at 0.9 and 2.6 ppm on average in the implanted spots at 4.5 and 8 nm, taking into account straggle values (1.9 and 3.1 nm) and creation yields (0.17 and 0.8% [50]).

Optical characterization

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra and decay measurements For PL spectra and decays, Er^{3+} ions were excited by 6 ns long pulses from a tunable (linewidth $< 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) optical parametric oscillator (OPO) pumped by a Nd:YAG Q-switched laser (Ekspla NT342B-SH). Green PL was collected and detected through a triple grating spectrometer (Acton SP2300) equipped with an intensified charge-coupled device (ICCD) camera (Princeton Instruments PI-MAX4) for spectra or a photomultiplier tube (S20 cathode) for decays. IR spectra and decays were measured with an InGaAs photodiode detector (FEMTO OE-200). Measurements at 10K were achieved thanks to a closed cycle helium refrigeration system (Helix CTI Cryogenics Cryodyne Refrigeration System Model 22) monitored by a LakeShore model 330 temperature controller.

PL mapping Emission from $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films ($^4\text{S}_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4\text{I}_{15/2}$ emission) and from shallow NV^- centers were mapped across the $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ sample surfaces by a confocal μRaman setup used in PL mode (Renishaw InVia) under continuous-wave excitation at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 532 \text{ nm}$.

NV^- centers optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR) To access the spin properties of the implanted NV^- centers, ODMR spectra were recorded by monitoring NV^- center PL intensity as a function of the applied microwave (MW) field frequency. Measurements were performed on a custom-made confocal microscopy setup with a high numerical aperture (NA=0.95) objective and green laser delivering $124 \mu\text{W}$ at 532 nm. NV^- centers' PL was spatially filtered through a $50 \mu\text{m}$ – pinhole and spectrally filtered by a 650-800 nm bandpass filter before detection by a single photon avalanche photodiode (Laser Components COUNT-10C and quTools quTag). A MW signal generator (SRS SG386) and a $100 \mu\text{m}$ diameter wire placed near the sample's surface were used to excite NV^- spin transitions at frequencies centered around 2.87 GHz. The MW power was 40 mW for the overall spectra and 1 mW for the high-resolution ones. A permanent magnet close to the sample created a field of about 1 mT that lifted the $m_s = \pm 1$ degeneracy.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

References

- [1] D. D. Awschalom, R. Hanson, J. Wrachtrup, B. B. Zhou, *Nature Photonics* **2018**, *12*, 9 516.
- [2] M. W. Doherty, N. B. Manson, P. Delaney, F. Jelezko, J. Wrachtrup, L. C. L. Hollenberg, *Physics Reports* **2013**, *528*, 1 1.
- [3] G. Balasubramanian, P. Neumann, D. Twitchen, M. Markham, R. Kolesov, N. Mizuochi, J. Isoya, J. Achard, J. Beck, J. Tissler, V. Jacques, P. R. Hemmer, F. Jelezko, J. Wrachtrup, *Nature Materials* **2009**, *8*, 5 383.

- [4] J. Achard, V. Jacques, A. Tallaire, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **2020**, 1–43.
- [5] M. Pompili, S. L. N. Hermans, S. Baier, H. K. C. Beukers, P. C. Humphreys, R. N. Schouten, R. F. L. Vermeulen, M. J. Tiggelman, L. Dos Santos Martins, B. Dirkse, S. Wehner, R. Hanson, *Science* **2021**, *372*, 6539–259.
- [6] T. H. Taminiau, J. Cramer, T. van der Sar, V. V. Dobrovitski, R. Hanson, *Nature Nanotechnology* **2014**, *9*, 3–171.
- [7] J. F. Barry, J. M. Schloss, E. Bauch, M. J. Turner, C. A. Hart, L. M. Pham, R. L. Walsworth, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2020**, *92*, 1–015004.
- [8] D. Rugar, H. J. Mamin, M. H. Sherwood, M. Kim, C. T. Rettner, K. Ohno, D. D. Awschalom, *Nature Nanotechnology* **2015**, *10*, 2–120.
- [9] M. Lesik, T. Plisson, L. Toraille, J. Renaud, F. Ocelli, M. Schmidt, O. Salord, A. Delobbe, T. Debuisschert, L. Rondin, P. Loubeyre, J.-F. Roch, *Science* **2019**, *366*, 6471–1359.
- [10] C. Bradac, W. Gao, J. Forneris, M. E. Trusheim, I. Aharonovich, *Nature Communications* **2019**, *10*, 1–5625.
- [11] S. Castelletto, A. Boretti, *Journal of Physics: Photonics* **2020**, *2*, 2–022001.
- [12] P. Goldner, A. Ferrier, O. Guillot-Noël, In J.-C. G. Bünzli, V. K. Pecharsky, editors, *Handbook on the Physics and Chemistry of Rare Earths*, volume 46, 1–78. Elsevier, Amsterdam, ISBN 978-0-444-82507-0, **2015**.
- [13] C. W. Thiel, T. Böttger, R. L. Cone, *Journal of Luminescence* **2011**, *131*, 3–353.
- [14] M. Rancic, M. P. Hedges, R. L. Ahlefeldt, M. J. Sellars, *Nature Physics* **2018**, *14*, 1–50.
- [15] D. Lago-Rivera, S. Grandi, J. V. Rakonjac, A. Seri, H. de Riedmatten, *Nature* **2021**, *594*, 7861–37.
- [16] J. Rochman, T. Xie, J. G. Bartholomew, K. C. Schwab, A. Faraon, *Nature Communications* **2023**, *14*, 1–1153.
- [17] A. Magyar, W. Hu, T. Shanley, M. E. Flatté, E. Hu, I. Aharonovich, *Nature Communications* **2014**, *5*–1.
- [18] J. Cajzl, P. Nekvindová, A. Macková, P. Malinský, D. Sedmidubský, M. Hušák, Z. Remeš, M. Varga, A. Kromka, R. Böttger, J. Oswald, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* **2017**, *19*, 8–6233.
- [19] V. Sedov, S. Kuznetsov, I. Kamenskikh, A. Martyanov, D. Vakalov, S. Savin, E. Rubtsova, V. Tarala, S. Omelkov, A. Kotlov, V. Ralchenko, V. Konov, *Carbon* **2021**, *174*–52.
- [20] V. Sedov, S. Kuznetsov, A. Martyanov, V. Ralchenko, *Functional Diamond* **2022**, *2*, 1–53.
- [21] N. Harada, A. Tallaire, D. Serrano, A. Seyeux, P. Marcus, X. Portier, C. Labbé, P. Goldner, A. Ferrier, *Materials Advances* **2022**, *3*, 1–300.
- [22] S. Gupta, Y. Huang, S. Liu, Y. Pei, N. Tamm, R. J. Warburton, T. Zhong, *arXiv* **2023**, arXiv:2310.07120.

- [23] T. L. Harris, Ph.D. thesis, Montana State University, **2001**.
- [24] T. Schröder, S. L. Mouradian, J. Zheng, M. E. Trusheim, M. Walsh, E. H. Chen, L. Li, I. Bayn, D. Englund, *Journal of the Optical Society of America B* **2016**, *33*, 4 B65.
- [25] T. Zhong, P. Goldner, *Nanophotonics* **2019**, *8*, 11 2003.
- [26] N. Harada, A. Ferrier, D. Serrano, M. Persechino, E. Briand, R. Bachelet, I. Vickridge, J.-J. Ganem, P. Goldner, A. Tallaire, *Journal of Applied Physics* **2020**, *128*, 5.
- [27] P. John, N. Polwart, C. E. Troupe, J. I. B. Wilson, *Diamond and Related Materials* **2002**, *11*, 3 861.
- [28] J. L. Jones, E. B. Slamovich, K. J. Bowman, *Journal of Materials Research* **2004**, *19*, 11 3414.
- [29] F. K. Lotgering, *Journal of Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry* **1959**, *9*, 2 113.
- [30] M.-H. Cho, D.-H. Ko, K. Jeong, S. W. Whangbo, C. N. Whang, S. C. Choi, S. J. Cho, *Journal of Applied Physics* **1999**, *85*, 5 2909.
- [31] S. J. Rhee, J. O. White, S. Lee, H. Chen, *Journal of Applied Physics* **2001**, *90*, 12 6110.
- [32] A. Fossati, S. Liu, J. Karlsson, A. Ikesue, A. Tallaire, A. Ferrier, D. Serrano, P. Goldner, *Nano Letters* **2020**, *20*, 10 7087.
- [33] N. Kaiser, *Applied Optics* **2002**, *41*, 16 3053.
- [34] S. Liu, A. Fossati, D. Serrano, A. Tallaire, A. Ferrier, P. Goldner, *ACS Nano* **2020**, *14*, 8 9953.
- [35] M. K. Alqedra, C. Deshmukh, S. Liu, D. Serrano, S. P. Horvath, S. Rafie-Zinedine, A. Abdelatif, L. Rippe, S. Kröll, B. Casabone, A. Ferrier, A. Tallaire, P. Goldner, H. de Riedmatten, A. Walther, *Physical Review B* **2023**, *108*, 7 075107.
- [36] R. D. Shannon, C. T. Prewitt, *Acta Crystallographica Section B Structural Crystallography and Crystal Chemistry* **1969**, *25*, 5 925.
- [37] R. D. Peacock, *Struct. Bonding* **1975**, *22* 83.
- [38] J. Zhang, S. Wang, L. An, M. Liu, L. Chen, *Journal of Luminescence* **2007**, *122-123* 8.
- [39] P. Kisliuk, W. F. Krupke, J. B. Gruber, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1964**, *40*, 12 3606.
- [40] N. C. Chang, J. B. Gruber, R. P. Leavitt, C. A. Morrison, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1982**, *76*, 8 3877.
- [41] M. J. Weber, *Physical Review B* **1971**, *4*, 9 2932.
- [42] F. Wang, R. Deng, J. Wang, Q. Wang, Y. Han, H. Zhu, X. Chen, X. Liu, *Nature Materials* **2011**, *10*, 12 968.
- [43] M. Inokuti, F. Hirayama, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **2004**, *43*, 6 1978.
- [44] M. Yokota, O. Tanimoto, *Journal of the Physics Society Japan* **1967**, *22*, 3 779.
- [45] M. J. Weber, *Physical Review* **1968**, *171*, 2 283.

Rare earth-diamond hybrid structures for optical quantum technologies: Supplementary Information

*Ionuț Gabriel Balașa** *María Alejandra Arranz-Martinez** *Pauline Perrin* *Midrel Ngandeu Ngambou*
Alexandre Hebbrecht *Diana Serrano* *Jocelyn Achard* *Alexandre Tallaire* *Philippe Goldner**

Dr. Ionuț Gabriel Balașa, (ionut-gabriel.balasa@chimieparistech.psl.eu), María Alejandra Arranz-Martinez, (ma.arranz-martinez@chimieparistech.psl.eu), Pauline Perrin, Alexandre Hebbrecht, Dr. Diana Serrano, Dr. Alexandre Tallaire, Dr. Philippe Goldner, (philippe.goldner@chimieparistech.psl.eu),
 Address: Chimie ParisTech, PSL University, CNRS, Institut de Recherche de Chimie Paris, 75005 Paris, France

Dr. Midrel Ngandeu Ngambou, Prof. Jocelyn Achard,
 Address: LSPM, CNRS, Université Sorbonne Paris Nord, 99 Avenue JB Clément 93460, Villetaneuse, France

†: these authors equally contributed to the work.

SI1 : Thin film textures, grain sizes, and thicknesses

Texture along the hkl orientation was calculated using the equations:

$$f = \frac{p - p_0}{1 - p_0}, \quad p = \frac{\sum I_{hkl}}{\sum I_{hkl} + \sum I_{h'k'l'}} \quad (1)$$

where the index 0 refers to the XRD pattern of a random powder. The sum over the I_{hkl} is performed over all reflections corresponding to the {hkl} family of planes whereas the sum over $I_{h'k'l'}$ runs over all other reflections. In our case we took into account all reflections in the 28 - 60° range for the reference powder and the (222), (400), (440), (622) peaks for the thin films, located at 29.23°, 33.86°, 48.62°, 57.72°, as the other ones are very weak and sometimes masked by spurious signals. Moreover, only peaks with a intensity above the XRD detector noise were taken into account. Texture values for all Er³⁺:Y₂O₃ films are reported in Table 1.

T_{dep} (°C)	$f_{(222)}$ (%)	$f_{(400)}$ (%)	$f_{(440)}$ (%)
550		95.6	
650		85.6	
750		94.2	
850			51.7
950	58.4		3.1
1000	67.9		

Table 1: Texture coefficients of Er³⁺:Y₂O₃ thin films along different orientations as a function of deposition temperature T_{dep} .

Thin film grain sizes d were determined using the Scherrer equation:

$$d = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos(\theta)} \quad (2)$$

where $K = 0.89$ is the shape factor, λ the X-Ray wavelength, β the XRD peak full width at half maximum (after subtracting the instrumental broadening), and θ is the peak position. For $T_{dep} \leq 750$ °C and

$T_{dep} \geq 950$ °C the (400), respectively (222), peak was used for the calculation. The size deduced from the above equation is therefore along the out-of-plane growth direction. In the case of the 850 °C sample, the (440) main orientation was considered. Samples deposited at 950 and 1000 °C showed too narrow reflections to reliably compute grain sizes, which are nevertheless above 200 nm.

SEM images were used to determine grain sizes in the thin film planes by counting interfaces along diagonals and medians and averaging the results. For the 550 °C film, the grains were too small to be evaluated.

Figure 1: $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin film thickness as a function of deposition temperature.

Figure 1 presents the thickness of $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films obtained after a 1 h long growth as a function of the deposition temperature. Thicknesses were estimated by ellipsometry (see the Experimental Section in the main text). The sample deposited at 550°C is much thinner because of the limited reactivity of the $\text{Y}(\text{TMHD})_3$ precursor with molecular oxygen, which drastically reduced the growth rate [1]. For temperatures between 650 and 950 °C we observed a larger and nearly constant (≈ 10 nm/mn) growth rate which significantly increased at 1000 °C in qualitative agreement with a mass transport limited regime.

SI2: Transitions between crystal field levels in visible and infrared PL spectra

Figure 2: $4S_{3/2} \rightarrow 4I_{15/2}$ PL in an $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ thin film deposited on diamond at room temperature (orange) and 10 K (blue). $T_{dep} = 850$ °C. Labels indicate the transitions between crystal field (CF) levels corresponding to the different peaks. The low-temperature spectrum shows only transitions from the lowest energy CF level E_1 to the Z_i ground state CF levels, whereas the room temperature one also includes transitions from the E_2 level. CF energies are in agreement with those reported in Ref. [2].

Figure 3: $4I_{13/2} \rightarrow 4I_{15/2}$ PL ($T = 10$ K) in an $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ thin film deposited on diamond at 750 °C. The observed peaks are assigned to transitions between CF levels for ions in the C_2 and C_{3i} sites, in agreement with [3, 4] and [4] respectively. The weak intensity of the lines originating from the C_2 Y_2 level indicates a low population consistent with the experimental temperature.

SI3: Green emission dynamics

Photoluminescence decays

Figure 4 and 5 show the green PL decays recorded at room and low temperatures as a function of deposition temperatures. The data were first fitted by single exponential functions over long time ranges. Second, these values were used to fit the complete decay with Equation 1 of the main text in which only the $N_A\sqrt{C}$ factor was varied in addition to an overall amplitude. This was done to reduce uncertainty on parameters but resulted in a slight deviation between fits and experimental data at long times. For the sample deposited at 1000 °C, a single exponential was used to fit the decay over the whole time range both at room and low temperatures.

Figure 4: PL decays of the ${}^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transition recorded at 565 nm and room temperature following excitation at 520 nm in $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films grown on diamond as a function of deposition temperatures. Solid lines are fits to the experimental data (see text). The bottom right figure is a zoom highlighting the initial non-exponential behavior of the decay. The dotted line corresponds to the exponential tail of the decay.

Figure 5: PL decays of the $^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition recorded at 565 nm and 10 K following excitation at 520 nm in $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films grown on diamond as a function of deposition temperatures. Solid lines are fits to the experimental data (see text). The bottom right figure is a zoom highlighting the initial non-exponential behavior of the decay. The dotted line corresponds to the exponential tail of the decay.

Cross-relaxation and energy migration

Figure 6 illustrates the cross-relaxations and energy migration processes that explain the PL decays presented in the main text and Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 6: (a) Er³⁺ energy levels (ions in C₂ sites) involved in cross-relaxation (CR) and energy migration (EM) processes. (b) The initial part of the decays corresponds to CR processes between excited Er³⁺ ions (donors, D) relaxing towards other Er³⁺ ions in the ground state (acceptors, A). (c) The exponential tail of the decays is explained by EM between Er³⁺ ions (D) followed by CR between D and A as in (b).

In more detail, the cross-relaxations (CR) affecting the populations of the ⁴S_{3/2} level appear in different combinations:

1. (⁴S_{3/2}, ⁴I_{15/2}) → (⁴I_{13/2}, ⁴I_{9/2})
2. (²H_{11/2}, ⁴I_{15/2}) → (⁴I_{13/2}, ⁴I_{9/2})
3. (⁴S_{3/2}, ⁴I_{15/2}) → (⁴I_{9/2}, ⁴I_{13/2})
4. (²H_{11/2}, ⁴I_{15/2}) → (⁴I_{9/2}, ⁴I_{13/2})

The ²H_{11/2} level can be involved at room temperature because it is thermalized with ⁴S_{3/2}.

Since the magnetic dipole transitions obey the $\Delta J = 0, \pm 1$ selection rule, the 1, 2, and 3 dipole-dipole CR must be of electric nature and thus only possible between ions in the C₂ sites. Indeed, electric dipole transitions are forbidden for the C_{3i} ions.

In addition, magnetic dipole transitions also obey $\Delta S = 0$ and $\Delta L = 0$. A free ion calculation shows that the ${}^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ level has a negligible contribution from the ${}^4\text{I}_{11/2}$ one (induced by the spin-orbit coupling) and thus the dipole-dipole CR 4 is also of electric nature and occurs only for the C_2 ions.

Figure 7 presents the expression $N_A\sqrt{C}$ (Equation 1 in the main text) as a function of the Er^{3+} concentration N_{Er} . Similarly to room temperature decays (Figure 2d of the main text), data suggest a linear dependence which is consistent with the $({}^4\text{S}_{3/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}) \rightarrow ({}^4\text{I}_{13/2}, {}^4\text{I}_{9/2})$ cross-relaxation between Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 site ($N_A = N_{Er(C_2)}$). This is illustrated in Figure 6a and b. The fit gives $C = 5 \pm 1 \times 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^6\text{s}^{-1}$.

Dependences of the long-time exponential tails of the PL decays are shown in Figure 8 at room temperature and 10 K as a function of Er^{3+} concentration. Decay rates at both temperatures can be approximated by a quadratic expression that indicates energy migration within Er^{3+} ions followed by Er^{3+} - Er^{3+} cross-relaxation (Figure 6a and c).

Figure 7: Low temperature energy transfer parameter of the Inokuti-Hirayama expression (Equation 1 of the main text) deduced from the fits of Figure 5. The Er^{3+} concentration depends on the film deposition temperature (see Figure 2c of the main text). The solid line is a linear fit of the form aN_{Er} which gives a value $N_A\sqrt{C} = 0.15 \pm 0.03 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $C = 5 \pm 1 \times 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^6\text{s}^{-1}$.

Decay rate temperature dependence

In the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin film deposited at 1000 °C, i.e. in the absence of energy migration and quenching, the decay rate of the ${}^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ level is expressed as:

$$W = W_{nr} + W_r = W_{0,nr}n^p + W_r$$

where W_{nr} and W_r are the non-radiative and radiative relaxations. The temperature dependence of W_{nr} is described by an effective phonon energy $\hbar\omega$ which determines the coefficient $n = (1 - \exp(-\hbar\omega)/kT)^{-1}$

Figure 8: Relaxation rates corresponding to the exponential tails of the decays shown in Figure 4 and 5 as a function of Er^{3+} concentration. The latter depends on deposition temperature (see Figure 2c of the main text). The solid line is a fit to a quadratic expression $a + b(N_{\text{Er}})^2$ corresponding to energy migration followed by cross-relaxation between Er^{3+} ions.

where k is the Boltzmann constant. The coefficient $p = \Delta E/\hbar\omega$ corresponds to the multiphonon relaxations process towards the level immediately below the probed one with an energy gap ΔE . At low temperature, $n = 1$ and we can directly determine $W_{nr} \approx 6000 \text{ s}^{-1}$ from the measured relaxation rate $W_{meas} = 1/167.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the radiative one $W_r = 1/700 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ estimated in [5]. These values, together with the one for the energy gap between the $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ and $^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ levels which is 2795 cm^{-1} , enable to compute the temperature dependence of W . As the $^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ level can be thermalized with $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ since they are separated by $\Delta E_t = 720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [6], a correction to the above formula can be introduced:

$$W = \frac{W + W' \exp(-\Delta E_t/kT)}{1 + \exp(-\Delta E_t/kT)}$$

where W' is the $^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ relaxation rate. It can be calculated in the same way as W using the parameters $W'_r = 1/78 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta E' = 3602 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $W_{nr}/W'_{nr} = \exp(-\alpha(\Delta E' - \Delta E))$ with $\alpha = 5.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [5, 6]. Despite the large value of W'_r , this correction is quite small as the $^2\text{H}_{11/2}$ population is only 3% of the $^4\text{S}_{3/2}$ one, even at 300 K. Adjusting the only free parameter $\hbar\omega$ to the room temperature measurement gives $\hbar\omega \approx 510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Figure 9). This is in line with previous studies that found values lower than the $\approx 600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ phonon cut-off frequency of the host [5, 7].

Figure 9: Calculated variation of the ${}^4S_{3/2}$ level relaxation rate as a function of temperature, taking into account thermalization with the ${}^2H_{11/2}$ level and an effective phonon energy of $\approx 510 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The circles are the experimental data measured in the $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin film deposited on diamond at $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

SI4 : IR emission dynamics

Photoluminescence decays

Figure 10 and 11 show the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ PL decays of the ions in C_2 and C_{3i} sites at 10 K in $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films deposited on diamond for different deposition temperatures. The data were fitted by single exponential functions except for the C_2 ion decays in the sample deposited at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for which a double exponential was used.

Figure 10: PL decays of the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transition of the C_2 ions recorded (excited) at 1535.5 (1528) nm in $Er^{3+}:Y_2O_3$ thin films grown on diamond as a function of deposition temperature. Solid lines are fits to the experimental data (see text).

Figure 11: PL decays of the ${}^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{15/2}$ transition of the C_{3i} ions recorded (excited) at 1548 (1530.5) nm in $\text{Er}^{3+}:\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ thin films grown on diamond as a function of deposition temperature. Solid lines are fits to the experimental data (see text).

Energy transfer and migration

Figure 12: (a) Er^{3+} energy levels [4] involved in energy transfer (ET) and energy migration (EM) processes for ions in C_{3i} and C_2 sites at low temperature. (b) Energy migration among C_{3i} ions (donors, D) is followed by energy transfer towards quenching centers like defects or impurities (acceptors, A). (c) Energy migration among C_2 ions (donors, D) is followed by energy transfer towards C_{3i} ions (acceptors, A).

We first discuss the decays of ions in the C_{3i} sites. In contrast with the green emission decays, they are all well described by single exponential functions, even at short times. The corresponding lifetimes tended to increase with increasing T_{dep} , i.e. decreasing Er^{3+} concentration (Figure 3e, main text). The lack of an initial non-exponential part in the decays indicates that the system evolves in a fast-diffusion regime [8]. Energy migration through the $(^4I_{13/2}, ^4I_{15/2}) \rightarrow (^4I_{15/2}, ^4I_{13/2})$ transfer within the C_{3i} ions is therefore faster than energy transfer towards quenching centers (Figure 12a and b). These quenching centers could include Er^{3+} ions in the C_2 sites. However, as the Y_1 level of C_{3i} ions is lower in energy than the one of the C_2 ions (Figure 12a), the $C_{3i} \rightarrow C_2$ energy transfer has a low probability. Indeed, it could only be evidenced in the sample with the highest Er^{3+} concentration ($T_{dep} = 650^\circ\text{C}$, Figure 13). We thus conclude that quenching centers such as impurities or defects on the surface or in the volume of the crystalline grains are mostly responsible for the relaxation of the $^4I_{13/2}$ level of the C_{3i} ions. A linear trend was found for $1/\tau_D$ as a function of $N_{Er(C_{3i})} = N_D$, suggesting that the quenching defect concentration N_A is independent of deposition temperature, since $1/\tau_D \propto N_D N_A$ (Figure 14, right and main text). As mentioned in the main text, quenching centers are likely to be in low concentration, as observed lifetimes are very long. We note that for samples deposited above 850°C , the experimental values (14.5 to 15.8 ms) are close to the theoretical value of 14.7 ms ([9]).

Er^{3+} ion in the C_2 sites also showed single-exponential PL decays, except for the sample deposited at 650°C which was well fitted with a bi-exponential function (Figure 10). The lifetimes of samples increased

with T_{dep} , reaching 8 ms at 1000 °C (Figure 3e, main text). This value is lower than the one of C_{3i} ions, due to an additional electric dipole contribution to the transition strength. As for the C_{3i} ions, the exponential behavior of samples with $T_{dep} \geq 750$ °C is attributed to fast energy migration followed by relaxation to quenching centers. The latter is attributed to the Er^{3+} ions in the C_{3i} sites since the Y_1 level of C_2 ions lies 42 cm^{-1} above that of the C_{3i} ions, making the $C_2 \rightarrow C_{3i}$ transfer energetically favorable. Indeed, it could be observed in the 950 °C film, which Er^{3+} concentration is only 0.3%. This mechanism is also in qualitative agreement with the variation of $1/\tau_D$ as a function of N_{Er} , which shows a quadratic behavior, i.e. $N_D = N_{Er(C_2)}$ and $N_A = N_{Er(C_{3i})}$, in contrast with the linear one of C_{3i} ions (Figure 14 left). For the 650 °C sample, the short time exponential component is attributed to the energy transfer towards the C_{3i} ions, as for the films deposited at higher temperatures. The exponential component at long times (12.7 ms) coincides with the lifetime of the C_{3i} ions. It is therefore ascribed to $C_{3i} \rightarrow C_2$ back-transfer. This is in agreement with the observation of C_2 ions emission after C_{3i} ions excitation in this sample (Figure 13). It is finally interesting to note that the $C_2 \leftrightarrow C_{3i}$ energy transfers are due to an unusual magnetic dipole-dipole interaction [10] as the electric dipole mechanism is forbidden for the $C_{3i} \ ^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow \ ^4I_{15/2}$ transition.

Figure 13: (a) Energy transfer mechanism between Er^{3+} ions in Y_2O_3 C_{3i} and C_2 sites at low temperature. After excitation, in the Y_2 level, C_{3i} ions quickly relax to the Y_1 level. Because the C_2 Y_1 level is 42 cm^{-1} higher than the C_{3i} Y_1 level, this process has a low probability. (b) PL decays of the C_2 ions recorded at 1535.5 nm after excitation of the C_{3i} ions at 1530.5 nm in the thin films deposited at 650 and 750 °C. Energy transfer is only observed in the 650 °C sample where Er^{3+} concentration is sufficiently high.

Figure 14: Relaxation rates of the ${}^4I_{13/2}$ level for the C_2 and C_{3i} ions (see Figure 10 and 11) as a function of Er^{3+} concentration. The latter depends on deposition temperature (see Figure 2c of the main text). The solid line is a fit to a quadratic expression $a + b(N_{Er})^2$ for the C_2 ions and to a linear one $a + bN_{Er}$ for the C_{3i} ions. In the case of the C_2 ions, this is attributed to energy migration followed by energy transfer to C_{3i} ions. For the C_{3i} ions, energy migration enables energy transfer towards quenching centers in constant concentration as a function of Er^{3+} concentration, i.e. thin film deposition temperature.

References

- [1] N. Harada, A. Ferrier, D. Serrano, M. Persechino, E. Briand, R. Bachelet, I. Vickridge, J.-J. Ganem, P. Goldner, A. Tallaire, *Journal of Applied Physics* **2020**, *128*, 5.
- [2] N. C. Chang, J. B. Gruber, R. P. Leavitt, C. A. Morrison, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1982**, *76*, 8 3877.
- [3] J. B. Gruber, R. P. Leavitt, C. A. Morrison, N. C. Chang, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1985**, *82*, 12 5373.
- [4] T. L. Harris, Ph.D. thesis, Montana State University, **2001**.
- [5] M. J. Weber, *Physical Review* **1968**, *171*, 2 283.
- [6] P. Kisliuk, W. F. Krupke, J. B. Gruber, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1964**, *40*, 12 3606.
- [7] Y. Repelin, C. Proust, E. Husson, J. M. Beny, *Journal of Solid State Chemistry* **1995**, *118*, 1 163.
- [8] M. J. Weber, *Physical Review B* **1971**, *4*, 9 2932.
- [9] C. Dodson, R. Zia, *Physical Review B* **2012**, *86*, 12 125102.
- [10] P. A. Tanner, M. Chua, M. F. Reid, *Chemical Physics Letters* **1993**, *209*, 5 539.

- [46] E. E. Brown, U. Hömmerich, A. Bluiett, C. Kucera, J. Ballato, S. Trivedi, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* **2014**, *97*, 7 2105.
- [47] J. B. Gruber, R. P. Leavitt, C. A. Morrison, N. C. Chang, *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1985**, *82*, 12 5373.
- [48] C. Thiel, T. Böttger, R. Cone, *Journal of Luminescence* **2011**, *131*, 3 353.
- [49] M. W. N. Ngambou, P. Perrin, I. Balasa, O. Brinza, A. Valentin, V. Mille, F. Bénédic, P. Goldner, A. Tallaire, J. Achard, *Materials for Quantum Technology* **2022**, *2*, 4 045001.
- [50] S. Pezzagna, B. Naydenov, F. Jelezko, J. Wrachtrup, J. Meijer, *New Journal of Physics* **2010**, *12*, 6 065017.
- [51] M. Xie, X. Yu, L. V. H. Rodgers, D. Xu, I. Chi-Durán, A. Toros, N. Quack, N. P. de Leon, P. C. Maurer, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **2022**, *119*, 8 e2114186119.
- [52] J. Achard, F. Silva, A. Tallaire, X. Bonnin, G. Lombardi, K. Hassouni, A. Gicquel, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics* **2007**, *40*, 20 6175.
- [53] A. Gritsch, L. Weiss, J. Früh, S. Rinner, A. Reiserer, *Physical Review X* **2022**, *12*, 4 041009.
- [54] A. Melville, T. Mairoser, A. Schmehl, M. Fischer, S. Gsell, M. Schreck, D. D. Awschalom, T. Heeg, B. Holländer, J. Schubert, D. G. Schlom, *Applied Physics Letters* **2013**, *103*, 22 222402.
- [55] A. Nandi, D. Cherns, I. Sanyal, M. Kuball, *Crystal Growth & Design* **2023**, *23*, 11 8290.
- [56] M. K. Singh, A. Prakash, G. Wolfowicz, J. Wen, Y. Huang, T. Rajh, D. D. Awschalom, T. Zhong, S. Guha, *APL Materials* **2020**, *8*, 3 031111.
- [57] M. W. N. Ngambou, P. Perrin, I. Balasa, O. Brinza, A. Valentin, V. Mille, F. Bénédic, P. Goldner, A. Tallaire, J. Achard, *Materials for Quantum Technology* **2022**, *2*, 4 045001.